

Scurvy described by the Faculty of Medicine at Copenhagen (1645)

Summary by James Lind (1772)

This is James Lind's English summary of a text on scurvy by the medical faculty of Copenhagen in 1645, the original is in Latin.

Yellow is used to indicate the description of the symptoms of scurvy.

This text is available at:

<https://10.5281/zenodo.17227207>

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<https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=2mkomzUAAAAJ>

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The faculty of physic at Copenhagen (b).

(b) It was one of the most celebrated faculties of medicine at that time in *Europe*; of which *Olaus Wormius*¹, two of the *Bartholines*², and *Simon Paulli*³ were then members. The latter, who was physician to the King of *Denmark*, has usually been ranked among the writers on the scurvy, upon account of an appendix which he added, *ann.* 1663, to his *Digressio de vera causa februm, &c.*

<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=ucm.5320216006&seq=574>

The text below is from Lind (1772; 3rd ed) p.357-361.

<https://archive.org/details/treatiseonscurvy1772lind/page/356/mode/2up>

<https://archive.org/details/b30511902/page/356/mode/2up>

<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=ucm.5320216006&seq=381>

<https://hdl.handle.net/2027/ucm.5320216006>

<https://wellcomecollection.org/works/r7fpbavt/items?canvas=379>

1 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ole_Worm
[https://doi.org/10.1016/s0025-6196\(12\)62537-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0025-6196(12)62537-3)
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/280805177>
<https://collections.nlm.nih.gov/catalog/nlm:nlmuid-101432400-img>

2 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Caspar_Bartholin_the_Elder
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Caspar_Bartholin_the_Younger

3 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Simon_Paulli

1645

Consilium medicæ facultatis Hafniensis de scorbuto.

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This was published for the benefit of the poor in the country, and is divided into four sections. The 1st recites the cause of the disease, and the signs by which it is known; the 2d, how it may be prevented; the 3d, how it ought to be cured; the 4th, what is proper for the removal of the chief symptoms.

Sect. 1. They observe, that it is a disease frequent among them and other northern nations. It attacks the patient in various shapes, according to his habit and constitution, or other diseases with which it may be complicated. Its immediate cause, is a bad digestion, owing to a crude, corrupted humour, oppressing the organs,

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both of the first digestion in the stomach, and of sanguification. Hence ensue for the most part difficulty of breathing, swelling, putrefaction, and bleeding of the gums; loose teeth; a weakness, swelling, and stiffness of the legs; spots, and the like. The external causes are, 1. The impure, gross, moist, and cold air of their country; those persons being most subject to it who live in the northern parts near the sea, or where they are surrounded with lakes. 2. Gross and corrupted food, viz. bad bread, not sufficiently baked, made of spoiled flour; salted and dried flesh and fish; old cheese; rancid butter; pease, and other grains, when spoiled; together with unwholesome malt liquors. 3. Those of a sedentary inactive way of life are most afflicted with it; together with those, 4. who are apt to be costive, or labour under a suppression of any natural evacuation; as also the low-spirited and dejected. 5. This disease often succeeds others; such as obstruc-

tions of the liver and spleen, and particularly quartan agues. It is likewise hereditary and infectious. From these external causes proceeds the internal or immediate cause of the disease before mentioned.

Although the scurvy may not easily be discovered in the beginning, by reason of its appearing under the form of other diseases; as also from its unexpected and slow at-

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tacks, (so that, in countries where it is prevalent, we are to suspect anomalous diseases not yielding to the usual remedies, especially if the patient is of a melancholy disposition, to be scorbutic); yet when the distemper is violent, it is easily known.

It is usually preceded by a lassitude over the whole body, weakness of the legs, difficulty of breathing when walking, a livid colour of the face, and by a greater sullessness of the habit of body. In its progress, flying heats become troublesome; the gums itch, with a great flow of saliva; the urine is sometimes turbid, at other times quite watery. When farther advanced, the difficulty of breathing is so great, that the patient cannot walk or move himself but he falls into a faint; of which he recovers when laid in bed. It is attended with colic pains; the gums are swelled, and bleed upon the least touch; the teeth are loose, and fall out without pain, the flesh at their roots being quite putrid; the breath is fœtid; the legs swell, and grow stiff, so that the patients cannot walk. Sometimes on the legs, and even over the whole body, there appear various red, purple, or azure spots. Now and then they are afflicted with the *St. Anthony's fire*, malignant ulcers, and nocturnal pains; and sometimes the body wastes away.

Different fevers, and various symptoms,

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almost of every kind that can be mentioned, often accompany this disease. The

urine is turbid, thick, and clayish, of a purple colour; but it does not long retain the same appearance. The pulse is variable; sometimes weak, at other times strong, when the patient seems very weak; and sometimes it is scarce to be felt. This disease is easily removed by proper remedies in the beginning; but when advanced, it is not so easy to prevent relapses. When proper diet and medicines are neglected, health is seldom restored. It commonly ends in a dropsy⁴ or consumption. A difficulty of breathing, and black spots on the legs, are dangerous symptoms; as also continual pains and flatulencies about the navel. An hereditary scurvy is seldom cured. It is a more dangerous disease in old persons than in young. When the mouth is affected, remedies are speedily to be used; otherwise the disease spreads farther, and may infect the whole throat. Fevers and ulcers accompanying this disease, cannot be cured without the assistance of antiscorbutic medicines.

Sect. 2. Prevention is proposed, by living in dry lodgings; fumigating the apartments with the steam of aromatic woods and gums; and by avoiding such food as has been ob-

served productive of the disease. For this is likewise recommended the use of a wine

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medicated with wormwood; and several other warm, bitter, aromatic ingredients. The body is at all times to be kept in a lax state, and the other evacuations (especially when suppressed) are duly to be promoted. Exercise, baths, physic in the spring and autumn, are also necessary. Those, who are much subject to it, are to take now and then two or three spoonfuls of an antiscorbutic water; which may be made more pleasant and stronger, by adding occasionally some of their scorbutic syrup, which is the same with *Forestus's*⁵.

Sect. 3. and 4. containing the indications of cure, and the treatment of the symptoms, have nothing new; the rules being pretty much the same as those of *Albertus*. The whole is concluded with a number of long prescriptions, adapted to the various intentions of prevention and cure. Here the prices of the several medicines are marked for the benefit of the poor.

4 Dropsy.

The historical diagnosis of dropsy – which is now obsolete – indicated simply an abnormal accumulation of fluid. The word derives from the Greek *hydrops* (water). Alternative or supplementary terms included *hydrothorax* (fluid in the chest cavity), *ascites* (which still indicates excess free fluid in the abdominal cavity), *anasarca* (still used to describe generalized edema throughout the body).

<https://doi.org/10.1017/CHOL9780521332866.101>

An ancient medical term used to indicate different conditions including chronic heart failure.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijcard.2017.07.104>

Scurvy can cause heart failure, eg.

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12890-024-02941-x> <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC10949735>

5 ... Or they may take the juice of scurvy grass mixed with wine; or their *elect. scorbuticum*, which is the conserves of several antiscorbutic herbs, with the addition of a very small quantity of *spir. vitriol*.